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Inventory, Action Plan and preliminary Set of Business Processes

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Deliverable 4.1

Deliverable

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<i>Abstract</i>	The purpose of this three-part-deliverable is threefold. First, it provides an inventory of operating acceleration services at Unite! and EPICUR partner universities. Second, it displays and explains the business processes that are part of the Agora platform. Third,

it offers an action plan for the implementation of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda.

History of changes

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v0.3	09 May	Michael Anger, Claudia Kramer, Kerstin Wedlich-Zachod in (KIT)		consolidation of the received feedback and review

Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiries:

In its request for revision of deliverable submission, the project officer states that the document needs to be more readable and better link its various parts. Moreover, the concept of business processes needs to be more clear from the beginning. Finally, the revision requires a

stronger link between the Action Plan and its underlying methodology with the rest of the document.

The document now explicitly addresses these comments:

To improve the quality of the document, D4.1 in the introduction now sets out more clearly the scope of the document and how the distinct parts of the document relate to the overall objective of WP4. The business processes are now outlined in the introduction and will be explained in more detail in Chapter 3, which has been significantly revised overall. For the inventory and action plan, D4.1 now contains more detail on the underlying methodology. In addition, the documents have been strongly revised to improve overall readability, consistency and usefulness and to embed them more clearly in the overall aUPaEU methodology.

Abbreviation list

Aalto	Aalto University
ALU	Albert-Ludwigs-University Freiburg
AMU	Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań
aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
BOKU	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CRM	Customer Relations Management
D2.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D5 from WP2, Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue
D3.2	aUPaEU deliverable number D9 from WP3, Report on the sustainability plan involving the Research & Transfer Services of the partners
D5.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D12 from WP5, Report on the implementation gap analysis and the ideation of the digital transition
D7.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D18 from WP7, First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPICUR	European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions
ERA	European Research Area
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HEI	Higher Education Institution
INP	Institute Polytechnique de Grenoble
ITIL	Information Technology Infrastructure Library
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology

KTH	KTH Royal Institute of Technology
PoliTO	Politecnico di Torino
RDM	Research Data Management
R&I	Research and innovation
SDU	University of Southern Denmark
TU Graz	Graz University of Technology
TUDa	Technical University of Darmstadt
UHA	Université Haute Alsace
ULisboa	Universidade de Lisboa
UniStra	University of Strasbourg
Unite!	University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering
UPC	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
UvA	University of Amsterdam
WP	Work Package
WUST	Wrocław University of Science and Technology

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1 Introduction

The **European Research Area (ERA)** constitutes a common scientific and technological area for the EU. Following the ideas of a market for research and innovation, free movement of researchers and students, exchange of scientific knowledge, and accelerated innovation, the ERA promises not only scientific excellence, but also a boost for innovation, a more competitive industry, and a promotion of European identity. However, the progress towards ERA objectives and implementation has been slowing down recently and there is room for improvement. At the same time, there is a widespread belief that universities, especially in the context of the [European Universities Initiative](#), can be important drivers for the advancement and integration of the ERA.

Following the European Commission's call for a [new European Research Area](#) and building on the initiative of the European Universities Initiative, the project "**A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities**" (aUPaEU) contributes to this ambitious endeavour by revitalising the concept of the ancient Greek Agora. The Agora, an open space where citizens used to meet, exchange goods and ideas, as well as engage in public discourse, was the main hub for social gatherings and economic transactions in ancient Greece. aUPaEU will recreate these functions by developing and providing a **digital Agora platform** to help to accelerate both the development of the ERA and the adaption of Higher Education Institutions (HEI). Using the Agora platform, different stakeholders can participate in and contribute to alliance communities, as well as provide and consume **acceleration services** that will support the institutional transformation of HEIs.

The term "acceleration services" comes from the entrepreneurial world, particularly the world of start-up ecosystems, where accelerators are programmes designed to speed up and support the growth of start-ups. Offering an array of resources and expertise, acceleration services aim to remove or mitigate challenges and bottlenecks that organisations face in their growth or developmental phases. As HEIs are organisations that face a number of comparable challenges, for example the ones described in the [Higher Education Transformation Agenda](#), acceleration services are also promising tools to support HEIs and alliances from the European Universities Initiative. Via the Agora platform, the aUPaEU project will offer a selection of tested acceleration services to boost institutional transformation of HEIs and alliances.

Scope and purpose of this deliverable

This document is the first deliverable by Work Package 4 (WP4) of the aUPaEU project. Titled **Coaching Service and Guidance for networks of HEIs**, WP4 has an overarching focus on conceptual and strategic objectives and covers a broad spectrum of tasks. This includes identifying, collecting, and implementing best practices for the Agora platform, as well as providing guidance for HEIs and alliances on how to adopt them. In the context of the overall Design Thinking Methodology of aUPaEU, WP4 defines service processes, identifies prevalent challenges and presents relevant insights and guidance as part of a top-down-approach, complementing the bottom-up efforts by other Work Packages (e.g., WP2, WP6). In order to provide a basis for this range of functions, this deliverable covers three purposes and therefore consists of three parts with distinct functions.

- First, it aims to identify, collect and highlight operating best practice acceleration services at Unite! and EPICUR partner universities (**Chapter 2: Inventory of operating Acceleration Services**). This way, the inventory sheds light on already existing practices at both alliances to guide the selection of potential acceleration services for the catalogue (D2.1) and the development of other project deliverables.
- Second, the document uses the information about operating services gathered by the inventory to provide examples for the potential business process of the Agora platform. **Chapter 3: Preliminary Set of Business Processes** starts from a conceptual point of view and describes the Agora as a system for planning resources and managing customer relations, which offers a systematic framework for thinking about the processes of supply of and demand for acceleration services on the platform.
- The third part of this document is a preliminary **Action Plan (Chapter 4)**, which initiates the establishment of a Coaching Service and Guidance for HEIs and alliances within the framework of WP4. The Action Plan contains recommendations for HEIs and alliances striving for institutional transformation based on the Higher Education Transformation Agenda, connecting the findings of Chapters 2 and 3 with a plan on how to utilise the Agora and its acceleration services.

Overall, the three parts of this deliverable provide three kinds of different resources: A) The inventory of acceleration services **offers empirical data** about operating services at EPICUR and Unite! partner universities and offers an outline of potential acceleration services to be implemented in the Agora platform. B) The Preliminary Set of Business Processes provides a **conceptual understanding** of the Agora in terms of its underlying processes and user relations, complementing the technical architecture of the platform outlined in aUPaEU's D5.1. C) In addition to these empirical and conceptual elements, the aUPaEU Action Plan provides a **preliminary recommendation** for HEIs and alliances on how to achieve institutional transformation in accordance with the Higher Education Transformation Agenda.

Altogether, these three elements provide different forms of guidance, e.g. on the inner processes of the Agora, on potential acceleration services and on how HEIs and alliances

can utilise these tools for institutional transformation. This document is primarily aimed at alliance project leaders, institutional coordinators and policy makers involved in change management and research management, but is designed to be accessible to all stakeholders seeking institutional transformation. As part of this, it presents an introductory explanation of how the Agora can be used to this end.

2 Inventory of operating Acceleration Services

This section assembles information on potential acceleration services at the partner universities of the alliances EPICUR and Unite!. Taking inventory of these operating services serves several **purposes**. First, it offers an overview of potential acceleration services to be integrated into the Agora, adding to understanding the state of the art, i.e. which services appear to be feasible, useful and of exemplary nature. Second, as a mapping exercise, this endeavour provides concrete examples to substantiate the notion of acceleration services. Third, this document gathers valuable information to inform other components of this deliverable (i.e. the preliminary set of business processes and the action plan). Fourth, this top-down approach serves as an input for the stakeholders' consultation aimed at obtaining the catalogue of acceleration services (D2.1). Finally, the inventory is a free-to-use source of information for all stakeholders interested in acceleration services, including service providers and users, members of university alliances, and policymakers.

In terms of **methodology**, the inventory is primarily about mapping services at EPICUR and Unite! partner universities that could qualify as acceleration services. Using a broad understanding of what could be acceleration services for HEIs, we followed the scope of the aUPaEU project to focus on acceleration services in the following areas of the ERA policy agenda: 1) Infrastructure and resource sharing, 2) Researcher careers, 3) R&I collaboration between academia and industry, 4) Open Science and 5) Citizen involvement. Based on these broad topics, we aim to identify different kinds of services in terms of training, platforms, infrastructures, resources and events. The inventory does not claim to be comprehensive and will be updated over the course of the project. For some institutions, the availability of information was limited due to restricted access to data or lack of translations of websites.

2.1 EPICUR partner universities

The European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions ([EPICUR](#)) is a university alliance committed to creating a unified and innovative European campus. As a part of the first generation of European University Alliances, EPICUR strives for closer collaboration, inter- and transdisciplinary teaching and learning, supporting early career researchers, as well as increasing mobility. In doing so, EPICUR aims to be a positive influence on European Society and become a role model for a distinctly European University.

Starting in late 2019, the nine EPICUR [partner universities](#) are jointly working to explore and test different approaches to connect study programmes, create virtual inter-university

campus environments, gamification approaches, strengthen European regions, and foster university community. As part of [EPICUR-Research](#), EPICUR also aims to develop common R&I strategies for the alliance, for example by defining [EPIChallenges](#), supporting collaborations between early career researchers, setting up EPIClusters, and more. EPICUR's vision of a future European University is to create a space characterised by mobility, interdisciplinarity, opportunities for students and early career researchers, inclusivity, and European tradition.

2.1.1 Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań (AMU)

Founded in 1919, the history of the [Adam Mickiewicz University](#) (Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu), located in Poznań, dates back to the 16th century, making it one of the country's oldest and most renowned universities. AMU offers a wide range of academic programmes across various fields, including humanities, social sciences, natural sciences, and the arts. The university's campus is equipped with modern facilities, libraries, and research centres that support academic and research activities.

As one of Poland's leading universities, AMU plays a vital role in the country's higher education landscape. It continues to attract students, researchers, and scholars from around the world and maintains a strong reputation for its contributions to academia and research.

Acceleration services at AMU at a glance

AMU harbours a number of acceleration services in various areas. One shining example is the [Poznan Science and Technology Park](#) (PPNT), which is a place where innovative companies, start-ups and entrepreneurial scientists can meet. The [AMU foundation](#) also offers supplementary courses in entrepreneurship while the [AMU Innovation](#) supports entrepreneurial teams from the academic community to create academic companies.

Furthermore, AMU runs several services and platforms to support its researchers, for example in the area of open science: While [PRESSto](#) provides a professional open journals platform for researchers, the repository [AMUR](#) helps to promote and disseminate research outputs. The [Educational Centre of Poznań University Library](#) supplements these services with training and support for the digital transformation of scientific activities.

Finally, AMU offers a broad and balanced spectrum of services that foster inclusion, work-life-balance, and other guidance, such as [AMU Welcome Center](#), a support office to implement the strategy of a [University Accessible for All](#), and the centre [Bilingualism Matters](#).

2.1.2 Albert-Ludwigs-University Freiburg (ALU)

[Albert Ludwig University of Freiburg](#) (Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg) is a prestigious institution of higher education founded in 1457, which makes it one of Germany's oldest and most respected universities.

In national and international university rankings, Freiburg ranks as one of the top five comprehensive universities in Germany and recognized as one of the top 100 universities in the world. The wide range of disciplines offered by the University of Freiburg holds great potential for innovative fundamental research, both within individual disciplines and in interdisciplinary collaborations.

Acceleration services at ALU at a glance

With its [Technology Transfer and Contract Office](#), [Start-up Office](#), and its [Start-up Academy](#) (“Gründungsakademie”), ALU strongly supports creating spin-offs, R&D projects with companies, and offers capacity building in the area of start-up qualifications and aims to establish a start-up-culture. An example of this is the [uniENTREPRENEUR](#) certificate for Bachelor students.

ALU also provides numerous [coaching services](#) in order to attract, train, and boost early career researchers, but also opens the university’s educational services to outside stakeholders, for example its [scientific education services](#).

The University regards itself as a place of diversity, inclusivity, and equal opportunities, which is reflected by a wide range of staff and services dedicated to uphold [gender and diversity](#).

2.1.3 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUPh)

[Aristotle University of Thessaloniki](#) (Aristoteleio Panepistimio Thessalonikis or AUPh) was founded in 1925 and carries the name of the famous philosopher Aristotle, who was born in the area. AUPh is the largest university in Greece and located at the centre of Thessaloniki.

AUPh's strategic goals remain ambitious within the framework of its vision and mission and are consistently geared towards continuing its tradition of being a pioneering institution that stands out among Greek and many foreign universities at all levels: Education, research, culture, connection with society.

Acceleration services at AUPh at a glance

In order to promote its graduated transition from university to work environment, AUPh offers career services, coaching, and facilitation as part of its [career services office](#). Furthermore, the [Centre for Lifelong Learning](#)'s programmes also address future business people.

Having invested significantly in tech infrastructure and expertise, AUPh also provides its large community of users with advanced services in the areas of networks, information systems, and electronic governance via its [IT services](#).

Lastly, AUPh's [library and information centre](#) supports a broad spectrum of teaching and research activities, for example by offering free resources, trainings, and workspace.

2.1.4 Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

The [Karlsruhe Institute of Technology](#) (Karlsruher Institut für Technologie), also known as the “Research Center in the Helmholtz Association” was established in 2009 through the merger of two distinguished institutions (Karlsruhe University and the Nuclear Research Center Karlsruhe) and has rapidly gained recognition as one of Europe’s leading technical universities.

From fundamental research to applications and technology transfer, KIT excels in a wide range of disciplines, for example in science, engineering, economics, and chemistry. KIT stands for close collaboration with industry and other stakeholders, fostering partnerships that contribute to its reputation for academic excellence and technological advancements.

Acceleration services at KIT at a glance

KIT’s dedication to industry partnerships finds testimony in several access points for companies and channels for collaboration, recruiting, technology transfer, and sponsoring. This includes the [KIT business club](#), [tailored learning services for industry](#), and a broad spectrum of offers by the [Innovation and Relations Management](#) Office.

To strengthen these ties between university and industry, KIT gives space to a number of services and programmes, for example business accelerators such as [KIT Gründerschmiede](#) (Founders’ Forge) and [upCAT](#), [start up competitions](#), educational [programmes and courses](#) on entrepreneurship and building business models, as well as [open spaces](#) for innovation.

Moreover, at KIT library researchers can find expertise in all Open Science matters, including [publication funds](#), coaching for [open access](#), and tailored [research data management training](#). The [House of Competence](#), the [Karlsruhe House of Young Scientists](#), and the [Training Centre for Technology and Environment](#) offer coaching and training programmes for researchers.

2.1.5 Université Haute Alsace (UHA)

[Université Haute Alsace](#) (UHA) is situated in the Alsace region of France, with its two centres in Mulhouse and Colmar. Established in 1975, it is a relatively young university with a focus on providing quality education and fostering research excellence.

While Université Haute Alsace may be one of the newer institutions in France, it plays an essential role in providing higher education and contributing to the region’s scientific and academic development, for example by offering tri-national courses.

Acceleration services at UHA at a glance

In terms of operating acceleration services, UHA has a strong lineup in the area of industry relations and entrepreneurship. The university maintains close ties with four so-called [competivity hubs](#), engages in [partnership-based research](#) in the Alsace region, and employs business incubators like [SATT Conectus](#) and [SEMIA](#), adding to its advance in value creation.

Furthermore, UHA seeks to sustain these developments by offering continuing professional development by the Adult Education, Research and Training Service ([SERFA](#)) or by [apprenticeship training](#).

Via its [project engineering programmes](#), UHA has also set in place measures to support scientific excellence. These training programmes go hand in hand with UHA's implementation of [HRS4R](#), the Human resources strategy for researchers.

2.1.6 University of Amsterdam (UvA)

Founded in 1632, the [University of Amsterdam](#) (Universiteit van Amsterdam or UvA) is consistently ranked among the world's best universities in global rankings. It is a top 100 university in the Times Higher Education Rankings, Quacquarelli Symonds Rankings and Leiden Ranking.

UvA has a diverse and international student body, fostering a dynamic and inclusive learning environment, which is also closely linked to the city of Amsterdam and its four campuses. UvA's partnerships with companies, social institutions, citizens and other stakeholders bring solutions to a multitude of challenges.

Acceleration services at UvA at a glance

An inventory of operating acceleration services at UVA reveals numerous activities in the area of industry relations and entrepreneurship, for example the [Innovation Exchange Amsterdam](#) (IXA), which offers expert guidance and advice on how to make academic knowledge available to the market and society. Other examples for activities in this area include the entrepreneurship laboratory [Demonstrator Lab](#) or [Amsterdam Venture Studios](#), which connects academia to the entrepreneurial community.

There are also several services providing coaching and training for researchers in terms of [career and networking](#), [funding allocation](#), and different kinds of [collaborations](#). Moreover, UVA introduced the [Impact Program](#), which helps researchers increase their social impact.

Via its [university library](#), UvA also offers resources, services and training for researchers for all matters of research, including Open Science.

2.1.7 University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU)

Vienna's [University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences](#), (Universität für Bodenkultur Wien or BOKU), has a specialised focus on natural resources and life sciences. Located in Austria and founded in 1872, it is one of Austria's leading universities in the field.

Key characteristics of the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences include its commitment to research in areas such as agriculture, forestry, environmental sciences, food sciences, and sustainable resource management.

Acceleration services at BOKU at a glance

BOKU is home to a number of different acceleration services in multiple areas. Besides its [technology transfer](#) and [stakeholder collaboration services](#), the university promotes entrepreneurship – e.g., via [awards](#) or [trainings](#) – and offers [coaching for funding allocation](#), while maintaining its commitment to sustainability.

Also worth mentioning is BOKU's [Research Information System](#) (FIS), which is a central and comprehensive database for research activities and outputs. In combination with its [document collection](#), BOKU provides its staff with a centralised information and resource system.

Finally, there are different services for [continuing education](#) and [personnel development](#), as well as [platforms for alumni](#) and [citizen science](#). BOKU also runs a [coordination office](#) dedicated to gender equality, diversity, and accessibility.

2.1.8 University of Southern Denmark (SDU)

The [University of Southern Denmark](#) (Syddansk Universitet or SDU) was founded in 1998 through the merger of several institutions, making it one of Denmark's younger universities.

SDU wants to promote sustainable development and research, for example through tailored research and education programmes, work with sustainability-promoting projects and initiatives for students and employees, and by implementing sustainable solutions and improving daily operations at the University.

Acceleration services at SDU at a glance

SDU's strong connection to industry has several indicators, with services like [SDU business lunch](#), [Company Meetup](#) for entrepreneurship connections, [SDU business partnerships](#) that help to promote companies, or [recruiting channels](#) with access to SDU graduates.

Furthermore, SDU actively engages with other stakeholders, for example the [SDU Research and Innovation Organisation](#), the [SDU Collaborative Services](#), or the Knowledge Centre, which also engages in [Citizen Science](#).

For its own graduates and researchers, SDU offers various pertinent courses and trainings, for example in [entrepreneurship](#), [funding and resource allocation](#), and many other areas as part of its [Counseling Centre](#). Via SDU's [Sustainable Development Goals Hub](#), the university documents its strategic alignment with progress towards reaching SDGs.

2.1.9 University of Strasbourg (UniStra)

The [University of Strasbourg](#) (Université de Strasbourg) is one of France's oldest and most renowned universities, with a history dating back to 1538. Due to its privileged location and exceptional heritage, the University of Strasbourg, recognised as a University of Excellence with a creative environment, is a magnet for international students and researchers.

The programme includes numerous faculties and research units. The Université de Strasbourg works in partnership with research institutions, public organisations and social players, enabling it to share and disseminate knowledge and maintain contact with society.

Acceleration services at UniStra at a glance

UniStra unites a number of acceleration services in different areas. Like the Université Haute Alsace (UHA), it is part of the technology transfer activities of [Conectus Alsace](#). [EM Strasbourg business school](#) not only provides entrepreneurship education, but also contributes to UniStra's strong commitment towards [internationalisation](#).

Moreover, UniStra harbours multiple services in the area of open science, for example in the form of tailored [open science trainings](#) or the open science platform [OSCAHR](#). There are also offers that help researchers and projects meet [funders' requirements](#) for open science, or counselling on [funding allocation](#) in general.

Finally, UniStra has its own [equality task force](#) to ensure inclusion, diversity, and accessibility.

2.2 Unite! partner universities

The University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering ([Unite!](#)) is a European University of [nine universities](#) committed to being a driving force for technology and innovation. Unite! partner universities share a [common vision](#) towards regional embeddedness, [inclusivity](#), technology transfer and education in engineering and science. Furthermore, Unite! aims to transform European higher education through multidisciplinary, multiculturalism, and multilingualism in teaching, research, and entrepreneurship.

With the development of a both virtual and physical, multilingual, and trans-European campus, Unite! aims to train the experts and leaders on digital and green transition. Unite! will

deepen and broaden its path to excellence in education, research and innovation, covering all European regions and combining 280,000 students and having more than 77,300 graduates annually.

2.2.1 Aalto University (Aalto)

Established in 2010 through the merger of three leading Finnish universities, [Aalto University](#) combines the areas of technology, business, and arts and design disciplines. It has gained recognition for its commitment to fostering innovation, entrepreneurship, and sustainability.

Key aspects of Aalto University include its diverse and internationally oriented student body, a strong focus on research and innovation, and a campus known for its modern architectural design. The university's mission is to address global challenges through cross-disciplinary collaboration and to prepare students to excel in a rapidly changing world.

Acceleration services at AU at a glance

Aalto hosts various best practices for acceleration services. Its [entrepreneurship](#) and [innovation](#) ecosystems are connected to and supplemented by a [start-up centre](#) with a pre-incubator programme, a [ventures programme](#) committed to advancing towards SDGs, and an [Innovation Services Unit](#). Offering experimentation facilities and infrastructures, the [Aalto University Industrial Internet Campus](#) (AIIIC) is a platform for students, researchers, and companies to innovate and co-create smart, connected products and services.

Additionally, Aalto hosts different internal search engines and catalogues, such as the [People and Services Catalogue](#), which serves a comprehensive database of the university's staff and services. This combines well with Aalto's coaching and training offers in the areas of [human resources](#), [learning services](#), and [information and skills services](#).

Another area where Aalto shows best practice examples is the area of open science support. Following the concept of an [Open University](#), Aalto offers various resources and [trainings](#), as well as open courses.

2.2.2 Graz University of Technology (TU Graz)

[Graz University of Technology](#) was founded in 1811. Key characteristics of Graz University of Technology include its commitment to cutting-edge research and a wide range of programmes in fields such as engineering, natural sciences, architecture, and technical mathematics.

TU Graz maintains a balanced relationship between knowledge-oriented and application-driven basic research, while cultivating a variety of collaborative models, for example in the form of public-private-partnerships or public-public partnerships.

Acceleration services at TU Graz at a glance

Due to its affinity to external partnerships, TU Graz operates a number of acceleration services in the area of industry relations. Examples of this include Strategic Partnerships for companies and [partner company status](#), a [career info service](#) that allows companies to promote themselves among graduates, funding allocation in the form of [sponsorships](#) and endowed professorships, scholarships, and more.

With the Forum [Technology and Society](#), the [TECONOMY](#), or career events like [Be Wanted](#), TU Graz also provides various platforms to connect academia and business. This also includes services for [apprenticeships](#).

2.2.3 Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble (INP)

The [Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble](#), located in France, combines a consortium of several top French engineering schools and research institutions in the Grenoble region.

Founded in 1900 with the creation of the Electrical Engineering Institute, INP benefits from its location in the Grenoble area, known as a hub of technological innovation and research in France. It maintains strong collaborations with industry partners and other research organisations, making significant contributions to the fields of science and engineering.

Acceleration services at INP at a glance

Having a strong emphasis on R&I, INP collaborates with a number of industry partners and fosters strong ties to this area. The efforts of entities such as [Ense³](#), [Phelma](#), or [INP Enterprise](#) offer potential best practice examples of this approach.

Furthermore, INP is heavily invested in a wide array of [technology transfer activities](#), including [research valorisation](#), and [incubation processes](#). As an offer for companies, INP also provides [access to its facilities](#) under certain conditions, adding to the opening of research infrastructures.

All of these activities go hand in hand with pertinent [training](#) and education offers. Lastly, students and early career researchers have privileged access to [job opportunities](#), [recruitment services](#), and [resource allocation](#).

2.2.4 KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Founded in 1827 in Stockholm, [KTH Royal Institute of Technology](#), has become a leading university in the areas of technology and engineering. KTH is Sweden's largest technical research and learning institution and focuses on both basic and applied research alike.

KTH is known for its strong ties to industry and other stakeholders, fostering collaborations and pursuing sustainable solutions to some of humanity's major challenges, such as climate change and energy supply.

Acceleration services at KTH at a glance

KTH's commitment to industry partnerships and R&I are well-documented by some of its operating acceleration services. For example, KTH fosters [collaboration between start-ups and industry](#) with its [Early Bird Network](#), and its [Business liaisons office](#). Furthermore, the KTH innovation offers [programmes](#), [awards](#), and [support services](#) promoting entrepreneurship.

All of these efforts contribute and connect to KTH's dedication to sustainability, which are expressed via programmes and services such as the [KTH business and community](#), the [Industrial Transformation Platform](#), and [other KTH platforms](#) in support of areas like digitisation. KTH repertoire also encompasses different services in the area of [open science](#) and support for [research data management](#).

2.2.5 Politecnico di Torino (PoliTO)

[Politecnico di Torino](#) was formally established in 1906 and was heavily involved in Italy's technical and industrial development as one of the country's engineering centres.

Key attributes of PoliTO include its commitment to cutting-edge research, innovation, and a diverse and international student body. The university offers a wide range of undergraduate and graduate programmes in various technical and scientific fields, including engineering, architecture, and industrial design. Among other things, PoliTO is highly regarded for its close collaborations with industry.

Acceleration services at PoliTO at a glance

As an institution that puts a lot of emphasis on technology, transfer, and entrepreneurship, PoliTO offers many different services in this area. Best practice examples of this include the [Enterprise and Innovation Center](#), incubators such as [I3P](#), as well as [trainings](#) and [competitions](#) to foster and promote entrepreneurship. Moreover, there are [joint PhD programmes with companies](#), [Challenges by Firms](#), and activities around [invention commercialisation](#).

This plentiful supply of services for companies also strongly benefits PoliTO's own staff and students, who profit from the rich offers in terms of [career services](#), [internship opportunities](#), and [information services](#) around calls, funding, and scholarships. But PoliTO also excels in other areas, for example [counselling](#) and [special needs services](#), as well as [open science](#) and [FAIR data](#), opening the institution in many different ways.

2.2.6 Technical University of Darmstadt (TUDa)

Since its founding in 1877, the [Technical University of Darmstadt](#) has been one of Germany's leading technical universities. TUDa is both dedicated to European integration and addressing the most pressing technological and scientific challenges.

TUDa's cutting-edge research is concentrated in the fields of Energy and Environment, Information and Intelligence, as well as Matter and Materials, where it follows large-scale, problem-based, and interdisciplinary approaches, in order to make collaborative efforts towards sustainable development.

Acceleration services at TUDa at a glance

TUDa harbours a set of acceleration services stimulating its potential for innovation. One prime example of this is [xchange](#), which provides a contact point for stakeholders who engage in [multidimensional exchange with TUDa](#), encompasses numerous [R&I activities](#), and offers [branding services](#) to companies. Moreover, via [Highway TUDa](#), the university runs a platform to catalogue and exchange innovations services and connect academia and industry. Via the funding programme [Pioneer Fund](#), TUDa increases its own capacity for innovation,

On top of that, TUDa supports academics and start-up founders with the [HIGHEST incubator](#), which hosts events like the [idea competitions](#) or start-up and [innovation days](#), enabling marketing, exploitation, and exchange. TUDa's stakeholder engagement also exceeds industry collaborations, and aims to initiate dialogue via its [public ecosystem engagement](#), which can be exemplified with the activities at the [WissKomm Campus](#). Finally, TUDa offers both infrastructure and expertise in the area of [research data management](#) and [Open Science](#).

2.2.7 Universidade de Lisboa (ULisboa)

Located in the capital of Portugal, [Universidade de Lisboa](#) (University of Lisbon) is one of the country's most prominent and comprehensive institutions of higher education. It has a rich history dating several centuries and acquired its current status in 2013, following the merger of the former Universidade Técnica de Lisboa and Universidade de Lisboa.

ULisboa is deeply involved with the Lisbon metropolitan area, and welcomes more than 1,000 foreign students every year. The quality of research, innovation and culture of the schools and research units at ULisboa attracts a growing number of international talents to create projects and research partnerships at the highest level.

Acceleration services at ULisboa at a glance

ULisboa offers some acceleration services in the area of entrepreneurship, such as its Entrepreneurship, [Innovation and Impact initiative](#), [entrepreneurship education](#), [business incubators](#), and [technology transfer](#) services.

Moreover, ULisboa staff has access to a [funding opportunities guide](#) and the participation in several contests to win [awards](#), both adding to potential resource allocation services.

2.2.8 Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

The [Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya](#) is located in Catalonia, Spain. Founded in 1971, it has gained recognition for its focus on science, architecture, engineering, and technology education and research.

UPC's mission is to contribute to a sustainable and fair world through research, technology transfer, and knowledge dissemination, while striving towards training competent professionals, proving excellence in research, and at the same time keeping territorial embeddedness.

Acceleration services at UPC at a glance

This mission directly translates into UPC's inventory of acceleration services. Starting with the area of entrepreneurship, UPC offers dedicated space to develop ideas via its [Emprèn programme](#), the [ESA IBC incubation centre](#), or [Parc UPC's](#) innovation ecosystem.

UPC unites numerous services for companies, for example in the form of tailored [corporate solutions](#) or other [company services](#) with facilitation mechanisms for [talent recruitment](#) and technology-related training offers, such as the [Tech Talent Center](#).

Furthermore, UPC is dedicated to promoting Citizen Science via its [UPC Citizen Science Portal](#), which while also engaging in Open Science via the [Aprèn platform](#) and the [UPC library's services and resources](#).

2.2.9 Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST)

[Wrocław University of Science and Technology](#) is a well-established institution of higher education with a strong focus on science, engineering, and technology. It traces its roots back to 1945 and has since evolved into one of Poland's most prominent technical universities.

WUST continues the tradition of prominent Polish universities and develops in close cooperation with the leading companies of Lower Silesia, conducting interdisciplinary research and education to meet the expectations of society and the economy.

Acceleration services at WUST at a glance

Through its [Innovation and Business Centre](#), WUST offers a space and infrastructure to develop business ideas, work with coaches, and build communities. In addition, the [Academic Enterprise Incubator](#) (AEI) promotes academic enterprises through events, organises workshops and seminars, and provides the framework conditions for entrepreneurship and business activities. In cooperation with companies, WUST offers [careers services](#) for graduates, which include training and networking.

WUST also acknowledges the importance of work-life-balance. In line with this, its [Center for Psychological Consultation](#) offers coaching and consulting for students and staff.

3 Preliminary Set of Business Processes

The primary output of the aUPaEU project is a platform that offers selected acceleration services. Stakeholders engage with these services for the most part in the form of processes of supply and demand, to which we generally refer to as business processes. The catalogue of acceleration services, derived from the bottom-up approach of stakeholders' consultation (Section 6 of D2.1), was employed as input to establish this preliminary set of business processes.

Following the “Dynamic Methodology for Acceleration Services Development: A Comprehensive Plan” described in D2.1 Section 5, this plan encompasses seven steps, including (1) stakeholder engagement, (2) requirement analysis, (3) data analysis, (4) business process definition, (5) implementation, (6) testing, and (7) dissemination. Each step contributes to the iterative development and refinement of acceleration services, aiming to meet stakeholder needs and drive innovation in the higher education sector.

In this plan, the **step 4**: “Business process definition” is coordinated by WP4. During this step, the business processes supporting the acceleration services are meticulously outlined using Business Process Modeling Language (BPML), thereby formalising the workflows that will be either automated or improved through the services. This formalisation establishes a structured approach to service delivery, ensuring consistency and efficiency throughout implementation. Additionally, a user guide is developed to assist non-technical users in effectively utilising the new services, thereby reducing the learning curve associated with adopting new technologies and processes. The comprehensive documentation generated in this phase ensures that every aspect of the service's business process is clearly defined and accessible, aiding in both implementation and ensuring stakeholders are fully informed about how the services will function and impact their daily activities.

In this preliminary set of business processes, we present an outline of the potential processes of the Agora platform, starting with a brief definition of the Agora's stakeholders and services (3.1), followed by a breakdown of the business processes of supply and demand (3.2). After extracting potential and actual business processes from insights of the previous chapter's inventory (3.3), the chapter concludes by outlining potential challenges for setting up the underlying business processes of the Agora (3.4) and setting up the aUPaEU Action Plan in Chapter 4.

The aforementioned **step 4** of the acceleration services development plan is an ongoing endeavour, continually evolving as we update the business processes and user guides on the [Notion platform](#). This platform enables us to deliver consistently updated information to Agora users conveniently, ensuring they have access to the latest resources and guidance.

3.1 The Agora: a marketplace where users meet services

The general approach of aUPaEU is to make the Agora platform and its acceleration services usable by and accessible for a wide range of stakeholders. It is a space designed to be open, inclusive, diverse and accessible. The stakeholder mapping process presented by D7.1 by WP7 identifies the core stakeholders, which are Universities belonging to the European Alliances Initiative, Unite! and EPiCUR as the initial focus group, following the preliminary analysis methodology presented in the initial outline of the catalogue of acceleration services (D2.1).

With the Agora platform being a marketplace for services and knowledge sharing, users from different stakeholder groups will be able to provide and consume acceleration based on their own needs. For example, extended stakeholders will strongly benefit from services fostering academia – business relations. Citizens can benefit from the platform in different ways, for example by participating in joint projects. Thus, the platform will offer services tailored to specific needs and facilitate collaboration and engagement with academic, industrial, and other stakeholders. Both academic and non-academic stakeholders will profit from exchanging and sharing of new ideas and information (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: Stakeholders engaging with the Agora. Icons © by iconmonstr.com

The Agora is a digital marketplace where stakeholders engage with each other by providing and consuming acceleration services. As described in more detail in D5.1, the Agora architecture resembles an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system, which sets up a platform for stakeholders' interaction via services.

Consistent with D2.1: Outline of the catalogue of acceleration services we use the ITIL terminology¹ and the handbook by Fitzsimmons² to describe the elements and properties of

¹ [ITIL](#) (Information Technology Infrastructure Library) by AXELOS is a best practice framework and the de facto standard for IT service management and addresses the management and development of online marketplaces. Our deliberations on service management in the Agora are referring to ITIL® Foundation, ITIL 4 Edition. (2019). United Kingdom: Stationery Office.

² For our understanding of services, we follow the book Fitzsimmons, J. A., Fitzsimmons, M. J. (2011). Service Management: Operations, Strategy, Information Technology. United Kingdom: McGraw-Hill.

services. Services are activities or sets of activities that take place in interaction between providers and consumers of services. The outputs of these interactions are not necessarily material, but provide solutions to customers' needs and problems (service utility). Services provide added value in different forms for their users, depending on their respective necessities. Users obtain value from access to goods, labour, skills, facilities, networks, information, systems, and other things that they purchase from the service provider. In contrast to other goods, users consuming a service usually do not take ownership of the components of the service. Services commonly are acts of co-creation by providers and users in particular environments (e.g., the service facility, the platform, etc.). In the case of acceleration services, these services could include training in entrepreneurship or career support for researchers.

The Agora as a platform is committed to create added value for its stakeholders (i.e. Agora users) in the form of acceleration services. In order to achieve this goal, it is crucial to properly analyse and understand these services in terms of the underlying business processes (which we aim to do in the following section). In doing so, aUPaEU will continuously assess the acceleration service offerings on the platform to evaluate whether the services meet the needs of its users and whether the solutions address them in an efficient way. For the purpose of this document, we consider acceleration services to fit the general description of services, but largely apply to the context of organisational transformation, i.e. the institutional transformation of HEIs and HEI alliances. The acceleration services investigated by the aUPaEU include 1) Facilitating resource and infrastructure sharing; 2) Promoting research professions and careers; 3) Improving R&I collaboration between academia and industry; 4) Boosting open science; and 5) Involving citizens and addressing societal issues. As outlined by D2.1, the catalogue of acceleration services will cover examples for all these areas and include a breakdown of different kinds of services, their expected outputs and outcomes, as well as the providers and users involved in the business processes. Before we provide concrete examples for both potential and actual acceleration services for the catalogue in Chapter 3.3, we introduce the general idea of the business processes in the following.

3.2 Business processes in the Agora platform

Making the Agora a place where stakeholders can provide and consume acceleration services demands a closer consideration of the different business processes involved and their implementation in an open platform. To obtain a better understanding of the potential business processes, we start by breaking down the main components involved. Figure 3.2 establishes the basic elements of Agora business processes and their interplay, which is crucial for developing business processes. By gaining access to Agora, all stakeholders can provide and consume acceleration services, becoming Agora users in different roles, for example as **service providers** as well as **service consumers**.

Figure 3.2: Providers, Consumers, and Management of Acceleration Services

The description of the business processes will be based on the different roles that **service providers** and **service consumers** play while participating in these processes. As we begin to delineate the various business processes within Agoras as outlined in the "Dynamic Methodology for Acceleration Services Development: A Comprehensive Plan" in D2.1, the mechanisms of supply and demand naturally emerge. In combination with the previous illustration, Figure 3.3 sketches the general framework of supply and demand within the Agora platform and provides an overview of the elements included in these processes. It becomes evident that the Agora platform serves a key role in these processes, acting as a facilitator of supply and demand and bringing together service providers and service consumers.

Figure 3.3: Supply and demand in the Agora of acceleration services

Drawing on these depictions of the general framework of supply and demand in the context of the Agora, WP4 will continue to analyse and illustrate business processes using the [Business Process Model and Notation \(BPMN\)](#). Doing so offers significant advantages in outlining the business processes of acceleration services within the Agora platform: It enables the visual depiction and documentation of the steps, activities, and interactions integral to delivering and utilising these services.

In the context of Agoras, where stakeholders interact to provide and consume acceleration services, BPMN can help in several ways. BPMN diagrams provide a clear visual representation of the steps and activities within acceleration services, aiding stakeholders in understanding the process flow. They also facilitate analysis, allowing stakeholders to identify bottlenecks and areas for improvement. BPMN offers a standardised notation language, ensuring consistency in describing business processes across stakeholders and organisations. These diagrams serve as a common language for communication between technical and non-technical stakeholders, fostering collaboration on acceleration service design and implementation. Additionally, BPMN diagrams can guide developers in WP5 in implementing business processes within the Agora platform by serving as a blueprint for integrating necessary functionalities. This standardised notation simplifies the representation of intricate business processes, facilitating stakeholders' comprehension and analysis of the workflow and is therefore essential for WP4's contribution to aUPaEU's overall methodology.

As outlined in the Dynamic Methodology for Acceleration Services Development in D2.1, WP4 defines and describes tangible and feasible business processes for the supply and demand of acceleration services (**Step 4**), for which applying BPMN is crucial. This step involves extracting requirements from the examples of acceleration services co-created in **Step 2**. During the first year of the project, the co-created acceleration services that have progressed through **Steps 2 and 3** include the provision of Agoras, research infrastructure services, R&I noticeboards, and showcases. The following figures represent the current status of the BPMN representation of the business process, which evolution can be followed up online on the [Notion platform](#).

Fig 3.4 depicts the business process of a generic acceleration service, establishing a threshold of 14 days for the interaction of stakeholders and 5 days to compile feedback. Similar business processes are currently being used in examples of acceleration services, such as stakeholders management enquiries, research infrastructures and R&I matchmaking noticeboard. This is the initial output of **Step 4** that will be tested and validated with user groups in **Step 6**, and will be improved iteratively, jointly with the implementation in **Step 5**. This business process will be adapted and tailored to any specific example of acceleration services that are processed by the seven steps comprehensive plan of acceleration service development described in D2.1. Currently there are about **20 acceleration services developments** that have initiated this plan, of which more details are provided in Section 5.1 of D5.1.

Fig 3.2 BPMN for a generic acceleration service

3.3 Insights from operating services for business processes

Furthermore, it is beneficial to revisit the inventory of existing best practice acceleration services at EPICUR and Unite! partner universities to explore tangible and feasible business processes for the supply and demand of acceleration services. Since the Agora is just starting to implement services and business processes, it is important to bear in mind that the examples described below largely follow operating accelerating services at partner universities. By emphasising their potential for the design of business processes, we will also provide some ideas on how to implement these processes as part of the Agora platform where possible. We structure our deliberations alongside the identified groups of acceleration services (section 3.3) and by highlighting some promising best practices.

3.3.1 Business processes for infrastructure and resource sharing services

Research infrastructures and other resources essential to conducting research are the backbone of science. Yet, these infrastructures are often highly specific and expensive to acquire, making infrastructure and resource sharing a topic of both growing importance and growing need for acceleration services. The Agora will allow contributing and listing the resources and infrastructures available (as providers) and consuming those required infrastructural resources (as consumers).

Usage of catalogue of research infrastructures	
Providers roles: service manager and infrastructure lead	Consumer role: faculty staff, researchers
Function of the Agora platform: On its frontend, the Agora makes available catalogues using search and filtering tools or AI recommendation systems by offering a user-friendly interface. The backend of the Agora acts as a server and manages, among other things, the underlying datasets of catalogues. To become a functioning and sustainable acceleration service with updated information, this service requires human and financial resources.	
Business process: The catalogue of research infrastructures is available at the frontend of the Agora platform. Business processes include the provision of and access to research infrastructures for researchers under certain terms and conditions.	
Best practice example: The Unite! Agora operates a catalogue of the alliance's research infrastructures. Co-created with the WP3 of the Unite! H2020 project, the catalogue services is one of the first acceleration services of the Unite! Agora.	

Opening research infrastructures to stakeholders outside academia	
Providers roles: service manager and infrastructure lead	Consumer role: researchers beyond academia
Function of the Agora platform: The availability of research infrastructure catalogues as part of the Agora unfolds its fullest potential in conjunction with services that facilitate sharing with stakeholders beyond academia. Via showcases and other communication activities, the Agora is able to promote accessible research infrastructures and provide them with reach beyond their host HEIs.	
Business process: While the general terms and conditions of infrastructure use and access can only be set by HEIs, the Agora can charge commissions for facilitating contact and transaction or broker coaching mechanisms for opening research infrastructures.	
Best practice example: Within the Unite! network there is a lot of expertise in opening research infrastructures to industry. For example, INP Grenoble has different schools and laboratories, such as Ense ³ or Phelma, that provide infrastructure components to interested stakeholders, with INP offering a general institutional framework.	

3.3.2 Business processes for research professions and researcher career acceleration services

The platform will facilitate stakeholder access to talent, as well as the circulation and supply of talent between universities and university alliances. At least equally important, these facilitating mechanisms also help to boost the careers of research and increase the appeal of professional paths in research. Depending on the respective acceleration mechanisms to be provided by the Agora platform, there are numerous examples of potential and actual business processes here. For example, the analysis performed in *D3.1: Report on available data sources* by WP3 shows pathways to develop catalogues of scientists, their skills, and research activities.

Career and recruitment events and services	
Providers roles: service manager and career provider	Consumer role: career seeker
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can connect and promote different job boards and career events or serve as a platform for these functions itself.	
Business process: Serving as either an intermediary via its matchmaking mechanisms or events schedule or providing the platform to host events like this itself, the Agora offers different ways to design processes for alliance researchers and companies.	
Best practice example: A number of EPICUR and Unite! partner universities are committed to offer career and recruitment events and services to students and researchers. Take, for example, SDU's business lunch bringing together graduates and companies, or UvA hosting numerous career events or showcasing open positions on its job board .	

Agora platform showcases	
Providers roles: service manager and showcase organiser	Consumer role: showcase service seeker
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora is a powerful communication and dissemination tool that can increase outreach for a number of entities and activities, for example by providing showcases as a service.	
Business process: Users can showcase their activities, projects, and outputs on demand to be highlighted on the Agora platform. A paid option can also be implemented for stakeholders outside the alliances, e.g., companies and society organisations.	
Best practice example: The Unite! Agora already started to include showcases to share experiences and best practices.	

Promotion of new job profiles	
Providers roles: service manager and job provider	Consumer role: job seeker
Function of the Agora platform: Much like other processes of academic advancement, acceleration requires resources and skills. The Agora can offer a prime example for the development of new platforms in need of skilled professionals to manage and maintain them.	
Business process: Assuming some level of success by the platform, the Agora can use its pioneering concept to promote and foster new strands of research (infrastructure) professions with broad and sought-after skill sets. Similar to the widespread recruitment of research data stewards, the Agora can promote research infrastructure stewards and promote this job profile with workshops, trainings, and other offers.	
Best practice example: In France, the profession of science engineers becomes more and more prevalent and offers academics stable career opportunities beyond research.	

Entrepreneurship programmes	
Providers roles: service manager and entrepreneurship programmes provider	Consumer role: entrepreneurship programmes seeker
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can promote and connect different entrepreneurship programmes, potentially contributing to community-building and improved interoperability.	
Business process: The Agora could establish a database of incubators, entrepreneurship programmes and resources available in the respective alliances, similarly to efforts in the	

area of Open Educational Resources (section 3.3.4). Moreover, the platform can help to promote these activities and foster international cooperation in this area.

Best practice example: The Unite! alliance has a rich expertise in and commitment to entrepreneurship, which is why its partner universities offer numerous courses and training in this area, for example at WUST's [Academic Enterprise Incubator](#).

3.3.3 Business processes around improved R&I collaboration between academy and industry

Opening the Agora to companies promises a number of benefits and added value for all stakeholder involved. While it is necessary to define a legal framework and concrete policies around industry access, the inclusion of industry stakeholders enables several potential business processes that can help HEIs and networks of HEIs to allocate resources for institutional transformations and develop new partnerships.

Strategic partnerships	
Providers roles: service manager and strategic partnerships proposer	Consumer role: strategic partnerships seeker
Function of the Agora platform: Acting as an intermediary and offering matchmaking between HEI and industry stakeholders, the Agora can build bridges between both groups of stakeholders and establish communication channels.	
Business process: The Agora can raise awareness for companies or HEIs looking to engage in strategic partnerships and help them to establish collaborations beyond their immediate ecosystem, for example in the form of events, showcases, or R&I matchmaking.	
Best practice example: Unite! and EPICUR universities usually maintain close ties with important industry stakeholders, especially in their regional environment. Examples of this include KTH's Business and Community platform or ALU's Business Unit of Science Communication and Strategy .	

R&I collaboration with industry	
Providers roles: service manager and R&I collaboration proposer	Consumer role: R&I collaboration seeker
Function of the Agora platform: With the R&I notice board, the Agora has a potent search engine to match R&I proposals and facilitate collaborations between science and industry.	

Business process: The Agora can keep track and promote different kinds of R&I collaborations within the alliances, disseminate best practices, and share events. The notice board also allows for matchmaking between stakeholders' offerings and needs.

Best practice example: there are several examples of R&I collaboration within Unite! and EPICUR, such as PoliTO's [joint PhD programmes](#) with companies, UPC's research-based corporate [solutions](#), or TUDa's [highway TUDa](#) platform.

Challenges by firms

Providers roles: service manager and challenges proposer

Consumer role: challenges seeker

Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can offer a platform where companies can pose challenges to be solved by teams of researchers (or students). As part of its frontend, the Agora could provide standardised templates to streamline the process.

Business process: In order to ensure authentic challenges and by providing a platform, outreach, and other related services, the Agora could charge commissions for posting challenges. By giving out awards or showcasing researcher or student teams successfully solving challenges, the Agora can also incentivise future challenge participation.

Best practice example: PoliTO's "Challenge by Firms" invites students to find solutions to challenges proposed by companies, addressing concrete technological or industry-related problems.

Industry sponsorship

Providers roles: service manager and industry sponsorship proposer

Consumer role: industry sponsorship seeker

Function of the Agora platform: The Agora platform can serve as a multiplier and facilitator for sponsorships, harnessing its range among different stakeholders, its information databases, and its matchmaking services.

Business process: Industry sponsorships can be both important tools for companies to promote their business and pathways for HEIs to allocate resources. Further potential outcomes are the development of strategic partnerships, R&I collaborations, and initiating other kinds of mutually beneficial transactions.

Best practice example: TU Graz offers industry partners various opportunities to promote their businesses among graduates and become sponsors of the universities, for example in the form of endowed professorships.

3.3.4 Business processes around the promotion of Open Science

Although the dedicated quest for open science is still a rather new development, it is arguably at the core of what science is all about. Open science already has a high impact on some scientific business processes, e.g. the area of publishing, but will continue to bring changes and give birth to new processes. In comparison to the [EOSC marketplace](#), the Agora's open science services have the advantage that they are tailored to the needs of stakeholders, describe the underlying processes in detail, and offer guidance and coaching for their implementation.

New open access business processes	
Providers roles: service manager and open access facilitator	Consumer role: open access seeker
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can promote alternative publication platforms and facilitate access for researchers.	
Business process: Many prestigious publishers now ask authors of open access publications to pay fees (APCs). The Agora can pool resources that can help authors in need of allocating resources or promote alternative ways of publishing scientific results.	
Best practice example: Independent institutional publishing platforms such as KIT Scientific Publishing can help to mitigate this development for researchers who are dedicated to Open Science, but do not have sufficient funding.	

Open science coaching mechanisms	
Providers roles: service manager and open science coach	Consumer role: open science coachee
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can promote open science coaching mechanisms and facilitate access for researchers. As part of its matchmaking services, the Agora can also connect open science professionals (e.g., data stewards) with stakeholders in need of their services.	
Business process: Open science coaching mechanisms could also be appealing paid-for offerings to companies that embrace open science or research data management (RDM) and want their data to be FAIR.	
Best practice example: KIT's service team for RDM offers training programmes and expertise in the area. Through the RDM Toolkit , researchers gain access to tailored presentations on demand. At Aalto University, there is also a network of data agents offering support for all kinds of stakeholders.	

Open education and open educational resources	
Providers roles: service manager and open education proposer	Consumer role: open education seeker
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can serve as a hub for open education and its respective resources, bolstering knowledge sharing and lowering barriers to learning. A catalogue of open educational resources could be one mechanism to allow for the supply and demand of services and resources in this area.	
Business process: Open education and open educational resources are free by default, leading to decreased costs of studying, improved accessibility, and enable knowledge creation and sharing. Furthermore, they increase the visibility of the providers of expertise and may lead to more collaborations.	
Best practice example: Aalto's commitment to open science can also be traced to its efforts in Open Education and Open Educational Resources, offering resources and guidance in these areas.	

Open data and open software catalogues	
Providers roles: service manager and open data proposer	Consumer role: open data seeker
Function of the Agora platform: Since the Agora can also provide a collection of databases and implement search engines, it allows stakeholders to browse catalogues of data and software publications.	
Business process: Modern evaluations of HEI performance increasingly include metrics for research data and software outputs. Similar to research infrastructures, the development of catalogues collecting reported data and software publications can be a valuable source of information for multiple stakeholders.	
Best practice example: In compliance with the Helmholtz Association's funding programmes , KIT increasingly monitors data and software publications and provides relevant guidelines for researchers to meet evaluation criteria and compete for open data excellence.	

3.3.5 Business processes based on acceleration services in the area of Citizen involvement

Citizens are among the extended stakeholders of the Agora, and making the platform accessible and useful to them is an important testimony of its societal relevance and contribution to the public good. The involvement of citizens not only allows them to contribute ideas, but also increases trust in science, connects HEIs to their regional ecosystems and warrants proximity to society's needs. For our vision of the Agora, it is

important for it to provide both solutions for relevant challenges and processes that bring about these solutions.

Identify and raise awareness of societal needs	
Providers roles: service manager and societal awareness proposer	Consumer role: societal awareness seeker
Function of the Agora platform: The Agora can raise awareness of certain societal needs as part of its showcases or connect citizens with other stakeholders, enabling them to raise awareness for public needs. Furthermore, HEIs and alliances can use the Agora to promote events featuring citizen engagement.	
Business process: Similar to business processes where companies can pose challenges for interested researchers and students to apply for, the Agora platform can offer similar options to societal organisations, e.g., city administrations.	
Best practice example: SDU's Citizen Science and Knowledge Centre is dedicated to creating value for and in collaboration with society to address the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.	

Citizen involvement in science	
Providers roles: service manager and citizen involvement proposer	Consumer role: citizen involvement seeker
Function of the Agora platform: As part of its matchmaking services or by promoting pertinent events, the Agora can serve as a facilitator for citizen science.	
Business process: Being in a position to bring together stakeholders in society and academia, the Agora can broker demands for research participation and involvement, raise awareness of pertinent activities, and help researchers who want to recruit citizens for research.	
Best practice example: UPC's Citizen Science Portal encompasses a number of activities in the area of citizen science and offers numerous opportunities for participation in research.	

Connect citizens with industry	
Providers roles: service manager and citizen connections proposer	Consumer role: citizen connections seeker
Function of the Agora platform: As a digital marketplace open to all kinds of stakeholders, the Agora's application is not limited to enabling connections between academia and outside stakeholders, but can also bring together citizens and industry, for example.	

Business process: Similar to processes for R&I collaboration, the Agora is in a position to facilitate and enable communication and transactions between different stakeholders, in this case citizens and companies. Via the platform's interface, users can get access to information about shared goals and interests or sign up to receive notifications on relevant developments.

Best practice example: A number of partner universities from EPICUR and Unite! already host events to connect their researchers and staff with companies, which can also be extended to citizens. For example, TU Graz's Forum Technology and Society or similar platforms offer inspiration to be applied to broader contexts.

The aforementioned examples outline different possibilities of business processes based on acceleration services offered via the Agora platform. The aUPaEU project will continue to identify and implement promising acceleration services into the Agora platform based on user feedback, while at the same time testing and assessing which services best support the institutional transformation of HEIs.

3.4 Potential challenges for the Agora and acceleration services

Acceleration services for HEI and HEI alliances are particular kinds of services that are still widely underexplored. While explaining their underlying business processes can improve our understanding of these services, it is crucial to recognize the challenges associated with implementing these services when developing business processes. Since we cannot address all the possible hurdles for the implementation of acceleration services and the underlying business processes, we want to highlight five pertinent challenges that demand consideration:

- 1) In the context of academia, many stakeholders are likely to be unaware of the numerous services available to them. While the Agora can play a key role in promoting certain services, it still needs to prioritise raising awareness for services and opportunities that may be useful, but are not on stakeholders' radars (**environmental challenges**).
- 2) Sometimes it may be difficult for service providers and managers to describe their services and the benefits that come along with them. The fact that acceleration services are a rather new development and not always easy to comprehend stresses the need for clarification and communication (**social challenges**).
- 3) Activities in the aforementioned area are also important to highlight the benefits for HEIs and HEI alliances and initiate the development of joint statements and declarations, for example in the form of policies. While commitment on the academic governance level can provide a big boost for business processes, lack of commitment

or lack of cooperation (e.g., due to a perceived infringement of HEI's autonomy), can pose major challenges (**political challenges**).

- 4) Acceleration services are, in many ways, still uncharted territory, which also holds true in a legal sense. Whereas some acceleration services are not new per se (for example in the area of infrastructure sharing or industry access), opening these services of HEIs to the larger contexts of HEI alliances and other stakeholders may be challenging and not only requires efforts on the level of HEI governance, but also balancing and enabling legal frameworks (**legal challenges**).
- 5) Lastly, the Agora platform's services and functions come at a cost. Since access and use for partners of HEI alliances should be as free as possible, the business processes mentioned before ought to be designed in a way that they are sustainable and ensure funding for the Agora for it to maintain its utility (**economic challenges**).

While the Agora itself can be considered a viable solution to various challenges and user needs in the area of HEI transformation, its implementation also poses challenges. By using a Design Thinking approach that combines empirical insights (i.e. user needs) with continuous testing and impact monitoring, the development of the Agora offers measures to address these challenges. Nevertheless, in order to unfold the Agora's fullest potential, its creation and implementation benefit from accompanying efforts, such as dissemination activities, developing joint policies and recommendations. As an example of the latter, the last part of this document will present the aUPaEU Action Plan, which is an early set of recommendations to provide guidance for HEIs striving towards implementing the Higher Education Transformation Agenda by making use of acceleration services.

3.5 Exploitation plan for the Agoras

As the aUPaEU project progresses, it's crucial to consider the future sustainability and growth of the Agoras once the project concludes, especially in supporting HEIs across Europe, particularly in widening countries. While the detailed exploitation plan will be included in the Task 3.6 Mapping a Sustainability Plan with the Focus Points Outreach, and Commercialization, starting at April 2024, and outlined in the forthcoming D3.2 , anticipated stakeholder interactions throughout the project's lifespan are expected to shape the business model of the Agoras. At this stage, marking the end of the project's first year, we can explore various potential business models that could ensure the sustainability of the Agoras. One such model is the premium model, which entails providing basic acceleration services free of charge while offering premium services, such as advanced AI recommendations or personalised human intervention, for a fee. This approach ensures accessibility to essential services while providing additional value-added options for those seeking more advanced features.

Another avenue to consider involves implementing a fee-for-expertise intermediation model. Under this framework, the Agoras would act as intermediaries, connecting HEIs with expert coaches and mentors based on their specific needs. In return for this matchmaking service, the Agoras would charge a fee, ensuring their sustainability while incentivising expert

engagement through financial compensation for their services. This model not only ensures the quality and relevance of the expertise provided but also fosters a mutually beneficial relationship between HEIs and expert professionals. The fact that the Agora is based on an ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system, makes it completely feasible to incorporate these business transactions into the Agoras.

These proposed business models may be applicable to both standalone Agoras and those integrated within alliances or collaborative projects. For example, university alliances, if established as legal entities, may choose to subscribe to Agora platform services to streamline their operations and enhance collaboration among member institutions. Similarly, collaborative projects among HEIs could allocate a portion of their budget to acquire Agora services tailored to their specific needs and goals.

However, it's essential to validate these business models rigorously, leveraging methodologies such as the lean startup approach. By using a build-measure-learn loop, the project can systematically test the market viability of the Agora business ideas, gathering feedback from stakeholders and adjusting the business plan accordingly. Furthermore, data generated from WP2 and WP6 will serve as invaluable input for informed decision-making during the project's final phases, ensuring that the Agoras are well-positioned for sustainable growth and impact beyond the project's duration.

4 aUPaEU Action Plan for implementing the Higher Education Transformation Agenda for HEIs

The last part of this document serves as an Action Plan directed at European University Alliances for a successful implementation of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda³. As such, it utilises early insights from the aUPaEU project to formulate a set of recommendations for HEIs and alliances striving towards institutional transformation and gives advice on how to deploy acceleration services such as the Agora platform for this purpose. While all of the recommended actions are preliminary, they launch the development of the Coaching Service and Guidance for HEIs and alliances, which is the overall objective of WP4. This chapter begins with a brief assessment of the background and prevalent challenges for HEIs and alliances striving towards implementing the Higher Education Transformation Agenda (4.1). It continues by explaining the rationale and the methodology of the aUPaEU Action Plan (4.2) and presenting its ten actions towards implementing the Agenda (4.3), before ending on some concluding remarks (4.4).

³ The Higher Education Transformation Agenda refers to the European strategy for universities, a [Commission Communication](#) adopted on 18 January 2022.

4.1 Background

Since its first [proposal](#) in 2000, the ERA became a policy framework and initiative to strengthen and coordinate research and innovation activities all across Europe. However, and despite major achievements, there are still significant challenges slowing down ERA's overall progress. These challenges also affect higher education institutions, which are important drivers of research, innovation and education, but are facing major challenges and institutional transformations themselves. The European Commission engages in numerous efforts to bolster HEIs and the integration of the ERA, for example via the [European Education Area](#) or the [European Universities Initiative](#).

Furthermore, the Commission aims to strengthen the R&I capacities of HEIs by outlining a Higher Education Transformation Agenda. Implementing this agenda requires a concerted action in empowering HEIs, strengthening collaborations via European University Alliances and supporting their institutional transformation. It is a call to EU countries and HEIs across Europe to join forces, e.g., in the form of European Universities, and seeks to develop a genuine European dimension in the higher education and R&I sector which is built on shared European values. However, as the [European Strategy for Universities](#) and other relevant documents such as the report [Progress of University Alliance Projects](#) show, there are still many challenges for the efforts of HEIs and HEI alliances, for example in the areas of sustainable funding, digitisation, recognition of qualifications, researcher careers, open science or mobility.

The Higher Education Transformation Agenda offers a strategic framework to enable all HEIs and HEI alliances in Europe to overcome these challenges, to adapt to changing conditions, and to continue the pathway to institutional transformation.

4.2 Rationale and methodology of the aUPaEU action plan

Bringing together the expertise of two first generation European University Alliances, Unite! and EPICUR, the aUPaEU project's **rationale** is to support institutional transformation. Both alliances already adhere to the Higher Education Transformation Agenda and implemented their own R&I Agendas ([Unite! R&I Agenda](#) and [EPICUR Research Agenda](#)), which makes it advantageous to build on their expertise in developing an action plan that supports HEIs with institutional transformations that implement the Transformation Agenda. As a project, aUPaEU will develop and share acceleration services for crucial areas of institutional reform and supplement them with methodologies, coaching services and digital technologies to facilitate institutional transformation. We strongly believe that the Agora platform combines these components in an advantageous manner and that alliances will benefit from utilising Agoras for the implementation of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda. Against this background, WP4 bundles initial findings of the aUPaEU project to outline ten actions for implementing the Transformation Agenda through the use of acceleration services via the Agora platform. Taken together, these actions are recommendations that anticipate the

development of a coaching service and guidance mechanisms for HEIs and alliances as part of aUPaEU.

Like the project as a whole, the methodology underlying these recommendations largely follows the Design Thinking Approach, which is described in more detail in section 5 of D2.1. It utilises preliminary project findings to develop an early draft of the actions recommended for institutional transformation in line with the Transformation Agenda. Our approach so far can be summarised in the following key steps performed:

- (1) **Empathise:** Building on the stakeholder mapping by WP7, the aUPaEU project seeks to understand the needs of different stakeholders who are potential users of the Agora platform. On the one hand, WP1 and WP2 gained valuable insights into user needs by conducting various meetings to inform the development of the Catalogue (D2.1). On the other hand, WP4 met with WP leaders from Unite! and EPICUR projects (e.g., Unite! H2020, EPICUR-Research) and institutional coordinators of the alliances to better understand the challenges they face and their expectations regarding aUPaEU and the Agora platform.
- (2) **Define:** Informed by these findings and project discussions, WP4 continued to analyse these observations and evaluated both key problems and potential solutions to be provided by acceleration services. The use of previous studies⁴ and analyses⁵ supported the definition of problems and pathways to transformation, while the inventory of acceleration services presented some ideas on how operating services can pose potential solutions.
- (3) **Ideate:** By thinking about the capabilities of the Agora platform's services and their conceptualisation in terms of business processes, and combining these ideas with observations from the inventory and findings from (1) and (2), WP4 started to brainstorm beneficiary actions for alliances aiming to use acceleration services for institutional transformation.

D2.1 already shows some potential **solution prototypes** (4) in terms of services. The **testing** stage (5) of these solutions, performed by WP6, will start after the publication of this document (see *D6.1: Draft report about the planned test with user groups*) and validate the Minimum Viable Solution of the Agora. An important limitation of this methodology and the Action Plan is therefore that they are preliminary and based on initial results. Nevertheless, by formulating this set of actions, WP4 lays a foundation for the development of coaching and guidance mechanisms to complement the Agora platform and to be refined over time.

⁴ Towards a 2030 vision on the future of universities in Europe:

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a3cde934-12a0-11eb-9a54-01aa75ed71a1/>

⁵ Knowledge ecosystems in the new ERA:

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8d536780-3025-11ed-975d-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

4.3 Ten actions towards implementing the Higher Education Transformation Agenda

Based on the aforementioned methodology, WP4 addresses university alliances on their path to institutional transformation in line with the Transformation Agenda and recommends the following actions. The Agora serves as a concrete tool to facilitate these recommended actions:

Action 1: Mapping and analysing alliance stakeholders and environment

It is important for both universities and alliances to recognise that they do not exist in a vacuum and that their approaches influence different stakeholders as part of their regional or network environment. It is therefore important to conduct a thorough mapping of the stakeholder ecosystem to identify relevant stakeholders, such as researchers, HEI staff, citizens, as well as partners from industry and business. The Agora is a powerful tool to manage stakeholder interactions via a community of users, fostering collaboration and facilitating exchange.

Action 2: Comprehensive assessment of user needs

Facilitating institutional transformation with acceleration services requires direction, which is why it is beneficial to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the needs of alliance stakeholders. This could include surveys or interviews with university staff, faculty, students, and other stakeholders to understand their primary concerns. Conversations with users can also fulfil this purpose. It is important to focus on the concrete needs of stakeholders when developing solutions to avoid top-down approaches that do not meet demands nor offer utility. The Agora allows direct communication with all the stakeholders by managing their enquiries, tracking the interaction with them, gathering feedback on this interaction about their enquiry and, finally, monitoring the assessment of user needs.

Action 3: Define priority areas for your HEI or HEIs alliances

Determine the current state of R&I activities in your alliance and define the key R&I areas that require immediate attention. This includes the identification of gaps, challenges, and opportunities for improvement. The [key objectives](#) of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda and the stakeholder needs identified in Action 2 may serve as a general assessment framework for this purpose. Prioritise them based on factors like societal impact, alignment with alliance strategies, and potential for collaboration. By compiling interactions, feedback, and monitoring of R&I activities, the Agora platform facilitates informed decision-making regarding the current state of these initiatives.

Action 4: Perform an inventory of relevant R&I capabilities in your HEI or your alliance

Gather information on the tools, services, and infrastructures that could foster R&I within the alliance. The Agora allows to create catalogues of relevant R&I capabilities, for example research infrastructures regardless of the Technology readiness level (TRL), internships,

training, PhD courses, proposals, looking for an overview of the existing or potential best practices. As a further step, it is advantageous to include a catalogue of acceleration services in these inventories, using the business processes described in Chapter 3 to better understand how these services work in practice and how they can best be utilised.

Action 5: Develop a framework for legal agreements

Assuming that University alliances have some joint strategies, policies, governance mechanisms and legal frameworks, it is important to consider and consult them at an early stage when planning the use of acceleration services for institutional transformation. The current landscape of R&I data exchange within the alliances is fragmented, with HEIs usually using their own tools. The Agora platform offers a single, collaborative platform that streamlines data exchange and simplifies legal agreements regarding data privacy. As many of the university alliances are not legal entities, one way of making legal agreements between alliances and the aUPaEU project to use the Agora platform could be at the level of the alliances' projects.

Action 6: Set up an inclusive digital community and foster stakeholder relations

EPICUR and Unite! are two examples of alliances promoting diversity, inclusion and mobility in order to reduce disparities and offer attractive academic environments with less barriers. Similar to the EPICommunity and the Unite! Metacampus, aUPaEU's Agora platform offers open digital communities accessible to a variety of stakeholders, offering spaces for collaboration and thriving R&I among internal stakeholders and external stakeholders. The business processes outlined in Chapter 3 are essentially processes that indicate ways to proceed with interactions between stakeholders in the Agora in order to provide and consume acceleration services.

Action 7: Promoting of Open Science, researcher careers and Citizen Science

Fostering Open Science is one of the priorities of the ERA and also part of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda. In order to adopt the EOSC's [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#), alliances can utilise aUPaEU's efforts towards developing recommendations and frameworks for joint Open Science policies or strengthen resource and capacity sharing by adapting catalogues of research infrastructures through the Agora platform. Furthermore, digital platforms highlight the need to think about new pathways for researcher careers in line with research assessment systems like [COARA](#), for example in the areas of research management, stakeholder management, or infrastructure sharing. Additionally, Citizen Science is an important tool to create public trust, engage with the regional ecosystem of HEIs and raise awareness for societal challenges.

Action 8: Ensure sufficient funding and sustainability

Institutional transformation requires resources and funding over time, which makes it necessary to outline how your HEI or alliance can allocate resources, for example in the form of funding, sponsoring, or other sources of income to ensure sustainability. Both the Agora

and the use of acceleration services can help to strengthen ties with business and industry by designing useful offerings, thus opening up new avenues of funding by providing and marketing R&I capabilities to external stakeholders while benefiting internal R&I activities. In order to be financially sustainable at the same time, the Agora platform can monetise these R&I capabilities to external stakeholders.

Action 9: Communication and dissemination

Develop a plan on how to communicate and disseminate your efforts towards institutional transformation, how to raise awareness of these processes and how to raise support from relevant stakeholders. Neither universities and research institutions nor university alliances exist in a vacuum, but are connected to different stakeholders who are part of these processes (see Actions 1 and 2). The Agora platform can become a showcase of the HEIs efforts towards institutional transformation, ensuring transparency, openness and engagement and avoiding top-down measures that stakeholders could perceive to be patronising or discouraging.

Action 10: Continuous monitoring and improvement

Carefully track the impact of all the above measures, evaluate their benefits and costs and do not hesitate to improve or change measures that do not bring tangible progress in the implementation of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda. This can be achieved by the Agora platform, which establishes a powerful and flexible tool for ongoing monitoring of R&I activities, introducing specific performance indicators and appropriate evaluation criteria.

4.4 Conclusion

The institutional transformation of HEIs in line with the Higher Education Transformation Agenda is a major challenge that requires careful planning and allocation of resources. Gaining stakeholder support, creating legal frameworks, and building HEI communities may seem like an insurmountable task, but it is not essential to constantly reinvent the wheel. On the contrary, it can be beneficial to observe and learn from more advanced alliances, identify operating good practices, and adopt them to manage changes.

Given the many different endeavours and initiatives, interoperability is key. Ensure that transformational efforts are in line with the ERA agenda and the strategy of the European University Initiative. While it is important to cherish multilingualism and international collaboration as part of the European Identity, it is also important to “speak the same language” when it comes to transformational efforts. Of course, there is no one-size-fits-all-approach for all HEI alliances, but transformation efforts should consider and learn from best practices. Evidence-based decision-making and stakeholder involvement go hand in hand in order to go forward with an approach that meets stakeholder needs. Involving key stakeholders within and outside HEIs not only enables an assessment of the needs of these stakeholders, but also provides valuable information and feedback on both the status quo and necessary actions.

The aUPaEU Action Plan provides guidance for the implementation of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda through the use of powerful tools such as the Agora platform and acceleration services. With the ten steps outlined in the Action Plan, aUPaEU presents preliminary recommendations to be taken up by the Alliances. These recommendations will be updated and refined as part of the work of WP4.